

E-HAILING TRANSPORT SYSTEM AND TRANSPORT MANAGEMENT POLICIES IN CITIES - A CASE STUDY OF LAGOS STATE

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Abstract

Man, by nature is a mobile being who moves around in search of livelihood and opportunities to better his lot. Mobility is central to man's existence, survival, thriving, and success. Man, nations, regions, and the world will be severely limited in their development strive, without a congenial environment, and one key factor in this regard is transportation. The ease with which people can commute within a city like Lagos State determines to some extent the livability and standard of living of the people in such a city, and it is in this regard, the advent of an e-hailing transport system is seen as a blessing, while some keen observers perceive it as an anathema, especially as regarding the future of transportation system in Lagos State. Using a quantitative approach, this study agreed that the e-hailing transport system has helped to redefine the transport system in Lagos State in terms of comfort, convenience, and ease of movement, nonetheless, it discovered based on the outcome of the investigation that it is not a sufficient solution to the management of transportation system in Lagos State. In response, the study recommends a mix of options for effective management of transport in Lagos State which include but are not limited to a mass transit system, effective train system, and e-hailing sharing besides suggesting various means through which the e-hailing transport system can be enhanced.

KEYWORDS: e-hailing, transport system, mobility, livelihood, development, transportation, standard of living, mass transit system, system theory.

1.0 Introduction

1.1 Background to the Study

Man, by nature is a mobile being who moves around in search of livelihood and opportunities to better his lot. Mobility, no doubt is central to man's existence, survival, thriving, and success. Man, nations, regions, and the world will be severely limited in their development strive, without a congenial environment, and one key factor in this regard is transportation. (Oyesiku, 2002).

There are several ways people move – some crawl, some walk, some ride animals, some ride bicycles, and some ride motorcycles, and tricycles. Some others board vehicles, some ships, and some airplanes. Some even engage in parachutes. In all, the goal is not to remain on the spot, because without such movements, opportunities will be limited, access to resources will be restricted, and life's existence will be threatened.

In fact, within a man's body composition, several movements take place. Movement is a fundamental aspect of life. Movement affects everything, from circulation to digestion to metabolism to immunity. With movement, our bodies regulate hormone activity, detoxify, and respire.¹ Movement is an essential activity that almost every if not all, man engages in daily. To move around, man has developed various means of transportation.

Transportation is one of the most revolutionized industries in the world today. To walk faster, man invented the skate, to travel faster on land, man leveraged fast-paced animals like horses and donkeys, before revolutionizing the transport industry with bicycles, motorcycles, and vehicles. Man yet unsatisfied decided to conquer the waters and invented paddle canoes, speed boats, and ships. The sky is no longer the limit, airplanes, aircraft, parachutes, and rockets, among others, have given man 'wings to fly'. The significance of all these inventions is that man is now more mobile than ever and at any time in history.

Unfortunately, however, intra-city traveling has remained a perennial nightmare in cities like Lagos. Commuting in cities like Lagos can sometimes be a 'hell' considering the number of hours

¹ Options for Animals (2023) - Importance of MOVEMENT! Published by Animal Chiropractic College in Wellsville, KS 4267 Virginia Rd, Wellsville, <https://optionsforanimals.com/importance-of-movement/>

motorists and passengers spend on the roads and in a traffic hold up. This is the reality of the modern world. This is the danger and challenges faced by most cosmopolitan cities like Lagos.

Robin Chase was right,

“Transportation is the center of the world! It is the glue of our daily lives. When it goes well, we do not see it. When it goes wrong, it negatively colors our day, makes us feel angry and impotent, (and) curtails our possibilities. It also consumes 17% of the average household’s income....”² (Schawbel, 2012). (Addition mine).

To solve the challenge posed by intra-city travel, individuals, government and non-governmental organizations as well as corporate organizations have devised various policies and means with mixed results. For instance, Tolu Ogunlesi (former Special Assistant to President Buhari on New Media remarked thus: *‘Traffic got so bad in Lagos in the 1970s (post-oil-boom) that the Govt had to introduce a policy where odd-numbered and even-numbered license plates were segregated according to Day of the week. Trust Nigerians —some got a second car, most others just got a second plate number’*. (Ogunlesi, 2019). This assertion was a confirmation of a discussion I had with my former principal – Hon Dayo Saka Fafunmi, a three-term member of the Lagos State House of Assembly. This policy is currently being used in Singapore while Lagos State is considering a re-introduction of it.

In Delhi, during the ministry of Arvind Kejriwal, private vehicles could be on the road only on certain days, depending on their license plate number, from January 1, 2016. The scheme aimed to reduce pollution and smog in Delhi. The scheme ended on November 11, 2017. The scheme came into force for the third time on November 4, 2019, after the success of the first two times. The results were visible from the very first day as the people of Delhi welcomed the move (India Today, 2015; Our Bureau, 2019).

² Robin Chase is an American transportation entrepreneur. She is co-founder and former CEO of Zipcar. She is also the founder and former CEO of Buzzcar, a peer-to-peer car-sharing service, acquired by Drivy.[2] She also started the defunct GoLoco.org, a vehicle for hire company. She is co-founder and executive chairman of Veniam, a vehicle network communications company. She authored the book, Peers Inc: How People and Platforms are Inventing the Collaborative Economy and Reinventing Capitalism

Similar policies were adopted in Beijing, China, and London in the United Kingdom. Prior to the 2008 Beijing Olympics, the city introduced a temporary road space rationing policy to check its pollution level by allowing odd-even plate numbers on alternate days with the exclusion of public transport and award of a 200 Yuan penalty for violators. The success of the policy in pollution and traffic management made the city implement the policy on a permanent basis after the Olympics. The city witnessed a 40 percent daily reduction in vehicle emissions. London adopted a similar approach to Singapore in 2003. It charged 11.50 GBP (Rs 1,166.85) to drivers for entering the “Congestion Charge Zone.”³

What the foregoing suggests is that transport system and management is a big issue in cities like Lagos, and of which several alternative measures have been adopted to curb traffic gridlock, reduce carbon emission, ensure affordable movement of residents, serve as means of income generation for the government and enhance the social and economic development of cities. Mass transit systems and alternative transportation systems such as water transportation, rail transportation, and air transportation are some measures put in place to promote efficient transportation in cities. *The e-hailing transport system* is one of the latest such strategies. The question is how effective has it been in promoting an effective transport management system in a city like Lagos State?

1.2 Statement of Problem

The challenge of managing the transport system in cities is a herculean one. This stems from the fact that cities are conglomerates of people. Lagos for instance has over twenty million population. Specifically and according to official figures and statements, “Lagos State is the smallest state in Nigeria yet, it has the highest urban population, which is 27.4 % of the national estimate [UN-Habitat]. According to the 2006 National Census, Lagos State has a population of 9,013,534 in relation to the National count of 140,003,542. However, based on the UN-Habitat and international development agencies’ estimates, Lagos State is said to have about 24.6 million inhabitants in

³ Some call this policy *Odd-even rationing*, some others call it *Odd-Even Formula*, some *Pico y Placa*, while some address it as *Circulation Alternée*. The idea is popularly known as road space rationing. The objective is mainly to reduce traffic flow on urban roads, based on the last digits on the vehicles’ number plates on certain days, and reduce air pollution. Read more at: <https://auto.economicstimes.indiatimes.com/news/odd-even-formula-how-these-cities-adopted-this-norm/50233506>

2015. The city is projected to have no less than 40 million populations by the year 2050. (Lagos State website, 2023)⁴

In 2016, Akinwumi Ambode, former governor of Lagos state was quoted to have said that ‘86 immigrants enter Lagos every minute of the day –the highest in any city in the world – and they have no plan to leave. Going by the above statement, Nigeria's economic capital receives 123,840 visitors on a daily basis’ (The Cable News, 2016)

Over 1.6 million vehicles ply Lagos roads daily according to the Lagos State Commissioner for Transportation; Dr. Frederic Oladeinde. Speaking at the 2019 Nigerian Bar Association General Conference in Lagos, Oladeinde revealed that among the 1.6 million vehicles, 226 cars run Lagos roads per km compared to the National average of 16 cars per km. He analyzed further that 75,000 commercial ‘Danfo’ buses in Lagos currently cater for about 10,000 public-passenger trips per day while an average of 12,000 public transport trips are generated daily. (Lagos State, 2023)

On August 18, 2022, The Premium Times reported that the city (Lagos) has over 1.4 million registered vehicles, and approximately 2.5 million vehicles are on the road daily, weekend inclusive. The paper further reported that a former Permanent Secretary in the Lagos State Ministry of Transport, Taiwo Salaam, has said if the traffic congestion in the densely populated Nigeria’s commercial capital city of Lagos should continue unaddressed till 2030, the city is estimated to lose as much as 21 billion dollars every month. This is because according to him, Lagos is currently growing at between seven and eight percent yearly, adding that the population growth percentage rate is 10 times faster than those of New York and Los Angeles cities in the United States of America. He added that Lagos currently accommodates 40 percent of the total registered vehicles in Nigeria. (Kanabe, 2022)

Traffic gridlock is one of the several challenges faced by urban managers in enhancing effective transport management systems in a city like Lagos. There are other issues such as how to promote affordable transport fares and reduce the number of carbon emissions on the environment, among others. It is therefore not surprising that urban managers and city administrators are always devising new policy measures to ensure effective transport management in cities, and Lagos is not an exemption in this regard. The question is how effective those measures are and what is the place

⁴ See <https://lagosstate.gov.ng/about-lagos/>

of the e-hailing transport system on effective transport management in cities like Lagos State? The question raised above represents the bedrock and focus of this study, and to which the entire study is devoted.

1.3 Research Objectives

- i. To find out the extent to which the e-hailing transport system has helped to enhance the effective management of transport in Lagos State.
- ii. To identify the challenges policymakers face in managing transport in cities like Lagos State.
- iii. To study the factors and challenges faced by e-hailing drivers and users in the use of e-hailing services as an alternative means of transportation.
- iv. To find out, if any, the best mode of transportation suitable for Lagos State.
- v. To find and recommend the various policy measures that can help to promote effective transportation in Lagos State, especially as relating to e-hailing transport.

1.4 Research Hypothesis

The hypothesis to be tested is as follows:

Hypothesis One

H_0 = There shall not be a significant difference between the opinion of males and females on the effect of e-hailing transport on the effective management of transport in Lagos State.

H_1 = There shall be a significant difference between the opinion of males and females on the effect of e-hailing transport on the effective management of transport in Lagos State.

2.0 Methodology

This study employs both quantitative and qualitative research methods. Using the qualitative research method, the study examines some relevant pieces of literature. On the other hand, the study employs quantitative methods through the use of a survey technique. The study employed a structured questionnaire to gather data on the e-hailing transport system in Lagos State, targeting both users and drivers. The questionnaire responses were supplemented with interviews. Two sets of questionnaires were distributed to approximately 100 to 110 respondents each, categorized by gender and role (user or driver). The survey focused on Lagos State residents, considering its

population growth. The sample size consisted of 210 respondents, split between genders and user/driver roles. Data gathered were presented using tables and graphs. This study analyzed the data gathered using the Pearson correlation coefficient on selected questionnaire responses.

3.0 Literature Review

In ‘URBAN PUBLIC TRANSPORTATION SYSTEMS’, Vukan R. Vuchic⁵ Professor, Department of Systems Engineering, University of Pennsylvania, Philadelphia, PA, USA emphasized the importance of Public Transportation in cities as against the use of private vehicles by private owners and ‘paratransit’. Categorizing public transportation into three categories using *Right of Way (ROW)*, he was of the view that –

Cities and metropolitan areas are centers of diverse activities, which require efficient and convenient transportation of persons and goods. It is often said that transportation is the lifeblood of cities. (The) high density of activities makes it possible and necessary that high capacity modes, such as bus, light rail and metro, be used because they are more economical, more energy efficient and require much less space than private cars. Moreover, public modes of transportation provide service for all persons, while cars can only be used by those who own and can drive them. Thus, cities need and benefit from public transportation services, which offer greater mobility for the entire population than people in rural areas can enjoy”.
(Vuchic, 2010 – emphasis mine).

Based on his findings and conclusion, there are different means of transportation which is available for urbanized cities like Lagos depending on the peculiar circumstances and situations, but he nonetheless favoured Light Rail Transit (LRT) ahead of other transit systems. According to him, “due to fully protected ROW⁶, category A - regardless of whether it is in tunnels, aerial or at ground

⁵ Dr. Vuchic is Emeritus Professor of Transportation Systems Engineering and of City and Regional Planning at the University of Pennsylvania in Philadelphia. He obtained his Ph.D. degree from the University of California at Berkeley in 1966. In 1967 he founded the Transportation Systems Engineering program at the University of Pennsylvania. He has also lectured at over 150 other universities and at many professional conferences. His research, focusing mostly on urban transportation systems, planning and policies, has been published in his “Transit Trilogy:” books, several of which have been translated into Japanese, Serbian, Russian, Chinese and Turkish languages. He has been consultant to U.S. Department of Transportation, cities of Belgrade, Beijing, Lima, Naples, Perth, Philadelphia, Rome, Singapore and transit agencies BART, WMATA, NYCT, SEPTA, TTC, Moscow Metro, and many others.

⁶ Vukan R. Vuchic (2010) description and categorization of **right of way** is as shown below:

level - rapid transit is by far the highest performance transit system. Independence from streets allows the operation of trains with up to 10 cars, having a capacity equivalence of 2-4 LRT trains or 15-25 buses. Operating speed is as high as the alignment of ROW physically allows, typically 2-3 times greater than the speed at which street transit operates. Consequently, rapid transit represents the highest-performance passenger transportation in urbanized areas. Correspondingly, the investment cost for rapid transit is very high, typically several times higher than for semi-rapid transit.” (Vuchic, 2010:2)

The advent of e-hailing transport services and embracement by residents of urban cities appears to contrast with the conclusion reached by Vuchic (2010). It seems the trend tends to support the use of e-hailing services compared to the public transit system. It is on this note, that we review another book.

To Dhawan & Yadav (2018)⁷, the e-hailing transport service is redefining the transport system in Indian cities and across the world. In ‘E-CAB HAILING: A STUDY ON CONSUMER BEHAVIOUR’; the two authors enumerated at least two advantages of the e-hailing service over the conventional modes of transportation, especially the ‘paratransit’.

Using both quantitative and qualitative approaches, Dhawan and Yadav (2019) are of the view in their study ‘that e-cab hailing ride sharing appeals to the younger generation because of less waiting time, point to point service, relief from the inconvenience of parking and drink and drive. It increases mobility options for people dwelling in cities. Ride-sharing seems to be complementary to the public transportation system.’

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- C - Urban streets with mixed traffic: Street transit modes include mostly buses, but also trolleybuses and tramways/streetcars.
 - B - Partially separated tracks/lanes, usually in street medians. Semirapid Transit, using mostly ROW B, requires higher investment and has a higher performance than street transit. It includes Light Rail Transit - LRT, as well as semirapid bus.
 - A - Paths used exclusively by transit vehicles comprise rapid transit mode or metro system. Its electric rail vehicles are operated in trains and provide the highest performance mode of urban transportation.

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It is instructive to note from the foregoing discourse that transportation is the lifeblood of cities, and its' effective management will require the adoption of different strategies and alternative transit mix.

3.1 Theoretical Orientation

The System Approach says that: any system is a single, unified system of interrelated parts or subsystems. Each part of the overall system is dependent on the others and cannot function optimally without each other will form the basis of my theoretical underpinning in this study. This approach has been used by several scholars. Gaál & Horváth (2017) used it in '*System Approach for Strategic Planning in Transport.*' It was earlier used by Jones & Joscelyn (1976) in '*A Systems Approach to the Analysis of Transportation Law*'.

The e-hailing transport system is a subsystem of transit systems in cities, and its utilities and challenges to the effective management of transportation in cities like Lagos State shall be the focus of our investigation using the system approach of public policy making concerning the system approach in (cities) transportation. This is based on the premise that both have their root in Ludwig von Bertalanffy's first 'General System Theory' which he published in 1968 (Ludwig von Bertalanffy 1968).

To a large extent, the system approach to transportation calls for the balancing of a 'multitude of solutions.' Thus 'the problems of transportation systems cannot be handled by only the tools of transport planning or traffic management.' It also presupposes that in a city, the transportation system should be taken as an integral part that must be properly planned alongside it. "Transportation is not constituted as the core of the state, but it has the same effect as the veins in a living body" and "...there is no such a sector in our public and private economy, which is not affected (by transportation). Sadly, it negatively affects sustainable city life. In this regard, Orosz (1993), cited in (Horváth & Gaál, 2017), had this in mind when he said that "the best (cheapest) trip is which does not happen."

Validly stated, "Széchenyi had discovered already in the 19th century the transport economics principle that transport demand is a derived demand, that is, it is generated by the spatial separation of socioeconomic processes. He expressively defined the economic axiom that a trip results in negative utility for passengers.... Essentially, 'the first step in properly managing the transport

system is the examination of transport demand (why people travel?) and the planning or development of the transport system as a technological system only could follow this phase (Horváth & Gaál, 2017). Transport demand depends on different places that have to be reached by the user and their spatial distribution as most transport models consider it in their trip generation phase. Traditionally simple linear correspondence can be demonstrated between the number of inhabitants, school children, jobs, shops of an area and departing/arriving trips” (Horváth & Gaál, 2017).

What the foregoing argument portends is that transportation is not just a derived demand necessitated by the settlements of men in a particular place, but that every travel an individual makes has a social cost to the society, and thus, all travels Lagosians make through the e-hailing platforms have social costs and benefits to the city of Lagos. This calls for the need for the Lagos State authority to harmonize the different transport systems within the State for the benefit of all Lagosians.

Like Horváth & Gaál (2017), I believe that “Transportation is not constituted as the core of the state, but it has the same effect as the veins in a living body” and “...there is no such a sector in our public and private economy, which is not affected (by transportation).

3.2 Conceptual Framework

The importance of cities to the modern world cannot be underestimated considering the pivotal role that cities play in today’s world. The city is one of the world’s biggest phenomena of the 21st century. It has evolved greatly over the centuries, particularly in terms of its size, form, structure, and composition, while largely maintaining its importance in local and regional development. In just 65 years, the world has experienced a population shift from rural to urban, as witnessed by an increase in the global population living in urban areas from 29.6% in 1950 to 54% in 2015. Estimates indicate that at the close of the monitoring period for the sustainable development goals in 2030, 60% of the world population will be urban. (United Nations, 2014).

Cities have become a positive and potent force for addressing sustainable economic growth, development, and prosperity. They drive innovation, consumption, and investment in both developed and developing countries. (Ibid). Lagos is home to over twenty million inhabitants, it is the most populous city in West Africa, the second largest city in Africa, and the 14th largest city

in the world. It is the economic nerve of West Africa and the commercial capital of Nigeria. When Lagos State sneezes, the rest of Nigeria States catch a cold. (Saumya, 2024)

At the heart of cities lies transportation. Cities and metropolitan areas are centers of diverse activities, which require efficient and convenient transportation of persons and goods. It is often said that transportation is the lifeblood of cities. (Vuchic, 2010:2). The rise of cities is attributed to several factors, out of which technology occupies a pivotal position. Transit systems are also needed in urbanized areas to make high-density of diverse activities, such as residences, business offices, factories, stadia, etc., physically possible while keeping cities livable and attractive for people. (Ibid).

Today, the Taxi market is very modern and provides a number of benefits to its users in terms of convenience, comfort, estimated traveling time, real-time information, economy, and safety. E-hailing of cabs (another term for e-hailing transport system) has become an essential element of metropolitan cities and they provide more customer value than most of the traditional taxi services. (Dhawan & Yadav, 2019:2)

In Nigeria and Lagos State, in particular, several e-hailing service providers exist. There is Uber and Taxify whose operations and structures especially as related to pricing are similar. Uber is a technology company that is providing services in over 140 cities across 40 different countries. Bolt has been in Nigeria since 2016. There is the inDriver too who apart from using web-based applications for processing traveling information between commuters and drivers allows the former to negotiate prices with the latter. Other e-hailing service providers include Rida Nigeria, SafeBoda, Shuttlers, Soole Rides, and others. (Business Day, 2022).

Of recent, the Lagos State Government launched the LagosRide, which is a mobility solution that will allow users to book and share the cost of a ride with similar transit patterns. It will link users up based on their preferred pick-up and drop-off points, each not more than 1km apart respectively, and a pick-up time not more than 5 minutes apart (**Lagos Ride, 2022**).

The thrust of this study is to examine the operation of some of these e-hailing service providers as alternatives to conventional means of transportation, and the impacts of the e-hailing transport system on the management of transportation in cities with Lagos State as a case study.

4.0. Result

In the course of the study, a total of twenty-one questions were raised. One of these questions was open-ended, while the rest were close-ended. Furthermore, the questions were divided into two segments. The first part was designed to generate biographical information about the respondents, while the second part asked direct questions relating to the respondents' experiences and views about the e-hailing transport system as a means of transportation in the city of Lagos. The responses to these questions are hereby presented in a tabular and pictorial form as shown below.

Question 1. A total of 128 questionnaires were distributed to both Males and Females both online and offline. There were 31 female and 17 male responses online. The researcher further distributed 80 questionnaires offline, 30 for females and 50 for males. The researcher was able to monitor the distribution and secured 24 responses for females and 38 responses for males to meet the target of the researcher.

Responses: Male = 55, Female = 55

Table 1 Questionnaire distribution among the respondents

Questions	Total Questionnaires Distributed	Returned Responses	Percentage
Male	61	55	50%
Female	67	55	50%
Total	128	110	100

Table 1 shows that the questionnaires were to a large extent evenly distributed between the male and female respondents to aid the purpose of the researcher investigation.

Question 2: Age Distribution

Responses: Table 2 below indicates that 39 percent of the respondents are between the ages of 21-30 years of age, 43 percent of the respondents are between the age of 31-40, and 41-50 years of

recorded 17 percent while only 1.1 percent of people above 50 years patronize the e-hailing platform. This outcome is instructive in that it indicates most people who patronize the e-hailing transport system are youthful population, and of which several factors can be adduced for this but chief among which is that such platforms are mostly powered by technologies that are youths friendly.

Table 2 The distribution of age of the respondents.

Age Parameters	Total Respondents	Percentage (%)
21-30	43	39
31-40	47	43
41-50	19	17
51 and above	1	1.1
Total	110	100

Education Status

As can be seen from Table 3 below, over 90% of the respondents are holders of first and second degrees, while less than four percent have an Ordinary National Diploma. The reason for this may be attributed to the researcher's purposeful distribution of the questionnaires among the educated members of the community in Lagos State. This is to ensure the respondents are people who are well-informed and knowledgeable enough to give informed opinions on the e-hailing transport system and its impact on transport management in a State like Lagos State.

Table 3: Educational Status of the Respondents

Educational Qualification	Total Respondents	Percentage (%)
OND	4	3.64
B.Sc. / HND	73	66.36
M.Sc.	33	30
Total	110	100

Employment Status

The outcome of the study shows that 53.64 percent of the respondents are self-employed people, 45.45 percent are employed people and less than one percent are people without jobs. This shows that income and wherewithal play a significant role in the patronage of e-hailing platforms by individuals. This is represented in Table 4 below.

Table 4: Employment Status

Employment Status	Total Respondents	Percentage (%)
Employed	50	45.45
Student/ Unemployed	1	0.91
Self-employed	59	53.64
Total	110	100

Riders (Users) / Drivers ratio

Even though the researchers made a conscious effort to reach out to riders on social media and also engage them physically, the study shows that it is easier to reach out to riders than drivers on these platforms. This outcome is instructive in that it shows there are more users of these e-hailing platforms than the driving operators on these platforms. Some of the users complained that sometimes, it is difficult to get drivers to transport them to where they are going in some period of the day and days of the week due to the shortage of drivers on these platforms. This perhaps accounts for what is termed 'surge' by e-hailing management which often translates to more income for the drivers, more commission for the e-hailing management, and extra pay for the riders. It also shows that there is still more business opportunity in the industry.

Table 5: Riders / Drivers Ratio

Categorization	Total Respondents	Percentage (%)
Riders (Users)	88	80
Drivers	22	20
Total	110	100

Question One

I use e-hailing transport which is easy, accessible, convenient, guarantees privacy, and is very secure than commercial buses and the drivers are more relatable.

Response

As shown in Table 6, over 97 percent of the respondents not only use the e-hailing platforms but equally believe is easy, accessible, convenient, guarantees privacy, and is very secure than commercial buses and the drivers are more relatable; while less than 3 percent believe otherwise. This outcome of the study proved at least two points – first, the respondents are people with knowledge of e-hailing operations, and second, most of them see e-hailing transport as a positive alternative to commercial buses popularly called ‘Danfo’ in Lagos State.

Table 6: E-hailing Platforms as being accessible, convenient, private, and secure

Categorization	Total Respondents	Percentage (%)
Yes	107	97.27
No	3	2.73
Total	110	100

Table 6 is graphically illustrated and reproduced below for further clarity.

Figure 1 Pie Chart of a number of people who believe that the e-hailing platforms but equally believed to be easy, accessible, convenient, guarantee privacy, and very secure than commercial buses, and the drivers are more relatable than the commercial (Danfo) buses.

Question Two

The e-hailing transport system is cheaper and more affordable than other means of transportation.

Table 7: Response of Pricing and Affordability

Categorization	Total Respondents	Percentage (%)
Yes	26	23.64
No	84	76.36
Total	110	100

Figure 2

Table 7 and Figure 2 shows that the users of e-hailing transport as a mode of transportation see it as more costly to use, yet many of them opted for it because of the perceived comfort, convenience, and security the platforms offer as demonstrated above and in their suggestions and recommendations.

Question Three

Payment on e-hailing transport is more difficult compared to other transportation modes in Lagos State.

Table 8: Ease of Making Payment on E-hailing Platforms compared to other transportation system

Categorization	Total Respondents	Percentage (%)
Yes	27	24,55
No	83	75.45
Total	110	100

In Table 8, the users and drivers of the e-hailing transport system see payment on these platforms as being easier compared to other means of transportation due to the possibility of alternative

means of payment aside from cash common to conventional commercial buses. Such alternative payment systems include e-wallet, Point of Sale (PoS), and Bank Transfer, among others. The respondents' responses are further illustrated graphically in Figure 3 below.

Figure 3: Level of Difficulty in Making Payment on E-hailing Platforms compared to other transportation systems

Question Four

Does e-hailing transport encourage the creation of jobs directly or indirectly for Nigerian youths?

Responses

Categorization	Total Respondents	Percentage (%)
Yes	110	100
No	0	0
Total	110	100

Table 9

Table 9, shows that all the respondents believe that e-hailing transport is a veritable means of generating employment opportunities in a city like Lagos State. The researcher further discusses some of the operators and shows that some drivers use it as a means of augmenting their collar jobs income since driving on these platforms is flexible.

Question Five

E-hailing platforms seem to extort the drivers on their platforms

Table 10: Possibility of extortion on E-hailing platforms

Categorization	Total Respondents	Percentage (%)
Yes	50	45
No	60	55
Total	110	100

Figure 4 Possibility of extortion of drivers by the e-hailing platforms

Using the pie chart, and the responses as tabulated above show that many of the riders believe the drivers are not being exploited, rather, some of the drivers usually exploit the riders through nefarious activities such as wrong billing. A rider for instance said:

“First of all you need to pay adequate attention to riders complains because drivers tend to be rude and also extort money from passengers.”

Question Six

The e-hailing transport system is a blessing to the effective management of transportation in Lagos State.

Categorization	Total Respondents	Percentage (%)
Yes	104	94.55
No	6	5.45
Total	110	100

Table 11

Figure 5: Chart showing the responses of people as to whether e-hailing transportation is a blessing or a curse in Lagos State.

As seen from the tabular representation and the pie chart sketch in Table 11 and Figure 5 respectively, the e-hailing riders and drivers believe that e-hailing transport is a blessing to the

effective management of transportation in Lagos State. Be that as it may, the over five percent who believe otherwise certainly have their reasons as will be indicated by other raised questions in the research.

Question Seven

E-hailing transport is better than other means of transportation in Lagos State

Table 12: E-hailing transport is better than other means of transportation in Lagos State

Categorization	Total Respondents	Percentage (%)
Yes	44	40
No	66	60
Total	110	100

As seen in Table 12, sixty percent of the respondents believe that e-hailing transport is better than other means of transportation in Lagos State such as commercial buses, ferry boats, canoes, and Bus Rapid Transit. With respect to the commercial buses, many of the respondents believe danfo buses are usually devoid of hygiene, lack privacy, and offer little comfort compared to e-hailing cabs. Some also believe that the ferry services and BRT are not easily accessible as they are restricted to certain places. The forty percent who think otherwise are of the view that e-hailing transportation is more costly. Some complained about the rudeness of some of the drivers of the e-hailing transport and sometimes their lack of personal hygiene too.

Question Eight

E-hailing transport has helped to improve the transportation system in Lagos State.

Responses

Categorization	Total Respondents	Percentage (%)
Yes	106	96.36
No	4	3.64
Total	110	100

Table 13

Figure 6: Figure 6 shows that the advent of e-hailing transportation in Lagos State has brought about the improvement of the transportation system in the State.

Table 13 and Figure 6 show that the advent of e-hailing transportation in Lagos State has brought about the improvement of the transportation system in the State.

Question Nine

Will you say there have been improvements in other means of transportation in Lagos State as a result of e-hailing transport as an alternative means of transportation?

Responses

Categorization	Total Respondents	Percentage (%)
Yes	87	79.09
No	23	20.9
Total	110	100

Figure XIV

Figure 7

In Table 14 and Figure 7, we see that nearly eighty percent of the respondents are of the view that e-hailing transportation has positively impacted other means of transportation; while about 20 percent believed otherwise.

Question Ten

Does the e-hailing transport system encourage hold-ups/traffic gridlock on Lagos roads?

Table 15: E-hailing Transport Creates Hold-ups

Categorization	Total Respondents	Percentage (%)
Yes	68	61.81
No	42	38.19
Total	110	100

Figure 8: E-hailing Transport Creates Hold-ups

A sizeable number of the respondents are of the view that the multiplication of e-hailing platforms and the increase in the number of e-hailing vehicles on Lagos roads will further compound the traffic gridlock and hold up in the State as indicated by the table and graph above. Precisely, about 70% of the respondents expressed their fears on the possibility of increased hold on Lagos roads as more people may be pushed to buy more vehicles for economic reasons of making extra income from e-hailing operations as drivers, dealers, agents, and even e-hailing platforms.

Question Eleven

Government regulation of the e-hailing transport system is hostile to the growth of the transport system in Lagos State.

Table 16: Perception of People on Government Policy on the E-hailing Transport

Categorization	Total Respondents	Percentage (%)
Yes	61	55.45
No	49	45.55
Total	110	100

As can be seen in Table 16, more than 50 percent of the respondents are of the view that government regulation is capable of inhibiting the growth of the e-hailing industry, while about 46 percent believe that the regulations put in place are needed to checkmate excesses of the operators and the management of the e-hailing platforms.

Question Twelve

The e-hailing transport system is reducing the challenges of transportation in Lagos State

Table 17: e-hailing transport system is reducing the challenges of transportation in Lagos State

Categorization	Total Respondents	Percentage (%)
Yes	85	77.27
No	25	22.73
Total	110	100

Figure 9: E-hailing transport system is reducing the challenges of transportation in Lagos State

Both the above Table 17 and Figure 9 indicate that over 70% of the respondents believe that the e-hailing transport system has helped to reduce the challenges of transportation in Lagos State; while about 23% say otherwise.

Question Thirteen

If available, I prefer public transportation like train, BRT, and ferry services to e-hailing transportation.

Table 18: Transportation preferences of respondents on E-hailing platforms compared to other transportation

Categorization	Total Respondents	Percentage (%)
Yes	51	46.36
No	59	53.63
Total	110	100

Figure 10. Transportation preferences of respondents on E-hailing platforms compared to other transportation

Table 18 and Figure 10 show that Bus Rapid Transit and Ferry Services are potential options for 46% of the respondents if available. A sizeable number of the respondents believe that the solution to the perennial traffic issue in Lagos State can be solved through the availability of train services, ferry services, and BRT buses. However, the absence and inadequacy of these alternative transportation means have made the e-hailing transport system a veritable option.

Question Fourteen

An increase in the number of e-hailing platforms and cabs will compound the problem of transportation in Lagos State.

Figure 11: Effect of Increase in E-hailing Platforms on Transportation in Lagos State

As seen from Table 19 and Figure 11, there is a palpable fear among the respondents that the multiplication of e-hailing platforms may further compound the transportation problem in Lagos State, especially in terms of traffic gridlock.

Question Fifteen

E-hailing drivers are sometimes exploited and cheated by riders (commuters).

Table 20: shows whether E-hailing drivers are exploited by the e-hailing platforms management

Categorization	Total Respondents	Percentage (%)
Yes	40	36.36
No	70	63.64
Total	110	100

Figure 12: shows whether E-hailing drivers are exploited by the e-hailing platform management

There is a divided opinion between the riders and the drivers of e-hailing platforms on whether the latter is being exploited or not. While almost all the drivers' respondents are of the view that they are being exploited by the e-hailing platforms, the riders believe that the drivers are getting a fair share of what is due to them. Some of the complaints are that 25% commission is too much to be deducted from them on every trip made.

4.2 Data Calculation, Analysis, and Interpretation

In a bit to further analyze the collated data, this research study shall employ the use of two statistical tools of the correlation coefficient. In particular, the Pearson coefficient correlation shall be used.

X	Y	XY	X ²	Y ²
38	27	1026	1444	729
38	31	1178	1444	961
29	29	841	841	841
31	39	1209	961	1521
41	35	1435	1681	1225
43	31	1333	1849	961
35	29	1015	1225	841
31	29	899	961	841
35	37	1295	1225	1369
29	25	725	841	625
39	34	1326	1521	1156
33	28	924	1089	784
29	26	754	841	676
30	34	1020	900	1156
31	36	1116	961	1296
41	33	1353	1681	1089
31	32	992	961	1024
38	29	1102	1444	754
32	31	992	1024	961

30	30	900	900	900
35	33	1155	1225	1089
32	31	992	1024	961
28	33	924	784	1089
35	29	1015	1225	841
33	28	924	1089	784
37	30	1110	1369	900
32	33	1056	1225	1089
33	32	1056	1089	1024
34	31	1054	1156	961
36	35	1260	1296	1225
30	32	960	900	1024
37	29	1073	1369	841
31	33	1023	961	1089
33	34	1122	1089	1156
35	31	1085	1225	961
32	32	1024	1024	1024
34	35	1190	1156	1225
38	36	1368	1444	1296
36	40	1440	1296	1600
31	38	1178	961	1444
32	37	1184	1024	1369
28	32	896	784	1024
29	35	1015	841	1225
33	31	1023	1089	961
34	34	1156	1156	1156
37	38	1406	1369	1444
30	30	900	900	900
33	32	1056	1089	1024
31	33	1023	961	1089

26	34	884	676	1156
30	35	1050	900	1225
41	37	1517	1681	1369
32	38	1216	1024	1444
34	36	1224	1156	1296
36	32	1152	1296	1024
1842	1794	60146	60461	59036

Table 21 for the correlation coefficient calculation.

Recall, the Pearson coefficient correlation

$$r_{xy} = \frac{n \sum x_i y_i - \sum x_i \sum y_i}{\sqrt{n \sum x_i^2 - (\sum x_i)^2} \sqrt{n \sum y_i^2 - (\sum y_i)^2}}$$

Where:

r_{xy} = Pearson r correlation coefficient between x and y

n = observation number

x_i = value of x for the ith observation

y_i = value of y for the ith observation

\sum = Summation (of variables)

$$\sum X = 1842, \sum Y = 1794, \sum XY = 60146,$$

$$\sum X^2 = 60461, \sum Y^2 = 59036$$

$$N = 55$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Coefficient of correlation (r)} &= \frac{55(60146) - (1842 \times 1794)}{\sqrt{55\{60461 - (1842)^2\}} \times \sqrt{55\{59036 - (1794)^2\}}} \\ &= \frac{3,308,030 - 3,304,548}{\sqrt{3,325,355 - 3,392,964} \times \sqrt{3,246,980 - 3,218,436}} \\ &= \frac{3,482}{\sqrt{67609} \times \sqrt{28,544}} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \frac{3482}{260 \times 168.95} \\
&= \frac{3482}{43927} \\
\text{Ans } (r) &= 0.079
\end{aligned}$$

Hypothesis Testing and Result Interpretation

Re-casting the Hypothesis, we have:

Hypothesis One

H_0 = There shall not be a significant difference between the opinion of males and females on the effect of e-hailing transport on the effective management of transport in Lagos State.

H_1 = There shall be a significant difference between the opinion of males and females on the effect of e-hailing transport on the effective management of transport in Lagos State.

Recall, when $r = 0$ means no relationship,

When $r =$ is negative such as -1 , it means a negative relationship and the null hypothesis is to be accepted.

When $r \geq 0$ or ≤ 1 means a positive relationship, which means the alternative hypothesis is to be accepted.

Thus, the result of the correlation coefficient 'r' above shows that there is a positive correlation between the e-hailing transport system and effective management of the transport system in Lagos State, but the relationship is **weak** based on the opinion of male and female respondents. This is because the correlation coefficient is positive but far less than 1 which ordinarily suggests a **strong perfect relationship**. What this further implies is that though there is a sort of divergence between the opinions of males and females, this divergence is insignificant and may be inconsequential. In specific terms, the opinions of males and females are very much the same on the operations of the e-hailing platform in Lagos State.

In essence, the **null hypothesis** is to be rejected, while the **alternative hypothesis** is adopted.

4.3 Discussion of Findings

Deductively, the findings of the study reveal that even though the e-hailing transport system has helped to improve the way people commute in Lagos State based on accessibility, security, comfort, and privacy; the fact is most Lagosians still perceive e-hailing as an insufficient measure to solving the problem of transportation in Lagos State. Suffice it to say, there are mixed feelings on the extent to which the e-hailing transport system can help to promote an effective transport system in Lagos State.

On one hand, a lot of the e-hailing transport users often view it as a pricier option, but they still choose it due to the perceived benefits of comfort, convenience, and security showcased in their experiences and feedback as seen in Table 1 where over 90% of the respondents believed so.

On the part of transport management authority, it is believed an unregulated e-hailing transport system will create more problems in the transportation sector of Lagos State especially considering the fact that many people may consider the economic prospects of e-hailing without or ahead of its associated social costs. This is because the underlying motive for businesses is profit-making and maximization. Without regulation of the e-hailing transport itself, there is bound to be a multiplication of e-hailing platforms with substandard services, and of which the users will be the greatest losers in the long run. To this extent, the government demands 'capitalization', that is, payment of registration fees of twenty-five million (₦25,000.00) is one way to standardize the process, even though this can result in 'oligopoly of the sector' as people such as business interests with better initiative may be wielded out due to lack of huge capital outlay.

On the part of the driver, it was suggested and discovered that a good means of payment and affordable e-hailing cars without deposit need to be provided for more youth who are willing to engage themselves. One of the core challenges affecting the drivers on the e-hailing platforms is bad roads and the excessiveness of road and traffic management workers. In addition, some drivers call for the establishment of a body that looks into the welfare of the e-hailing drivers such as scams, fair hearing, and security, among others.

Based on the data gathered, the involvement of the Lagos State Government is affecting the e-hailing space. In the view of some of the respondents, the government should provide a conducive atmosphere for

businesses to thrive, rather than competing with the private sector to make money in the same space. It is a counter-productive means of providing employment.

The findings also show that most riders call for more security measures that will guarantee their safety, and prevent extortions from the operators from both the drivers and the e-hailing management platforms. As the study reveals there is also the need for most e-hailing Drivers and Riders are not well informed about the rules and regulations governing the e-hailing platforms.

Also, there are several challenges associated with the E-hailing Transport System and transportation generally in a city like Lagos State, one of which is finding inappropriate pricing that will be acceptable for the important stakeholders in the industry. The riders want lower prices for good comfort and smooth ride. The drivers want higher commissions, hence, they complain about the amount being charged by the E-hailing platforms. The E-hailing platforms are not oblivious to the need to break even, beat their competitors, and meet regulatory obligations. These mutually exclusive goals and objectives cannot but continue to create challenges in the industry for a feasible future. Be that as it may, a midpoint and consensus can always be reached by the parties involved through mutual consideration of each party's interests.

The multiplication of E-hailing platforms is another big challenge, and its attendant consequences on road infrastructures, if left unchecked in the foreseeable future. It is important to note that when purchasing private vehicles is motivated by economic gain - profits making to be precise, then, there is a likelihood of an astronomical rise in the number of vehicles for such purposes, and their impacts on the roads in the form traffic gridlock, wearing off roads, and social costs to the society general.

Findings also show that the most used vehicle in the industry is the Toyota Corolla of between 2006 and 2008 models. This is because a lot of the operators believe the car is rugged and durable compared to other vehicle models besides the availability of its parts. It is therefore not surprising that these sets of vehicle prices are experiencing specific commodity inflation due to high demands, and this is equally rubbing off on their parts pricing. As of the period of this study, the current price of Toyota Corolla 'Tokunbo' is between seven million (₦7,000,000.00) and eight million (₦8,000,000.00) plus. This is on the high side, given the fact that the same sets of vehicles were bought for as low as one million five hundred thousand six years ago. This

researcher noted that he could sell his own Corolla vehicle which he bought six years back for one million five hundred fifty thousand (₦1,500,000.00) for as much as three million five hundred thousand (₦3,500,000.00) in today's market. While the researcher equally observed that there is a general increase in the prices of goods in automobile markets, his observations however proved that Toyota Corolla prices have quadrupled in recent years compared to other vehicle products. The social implication of this trend is that Corolla is no longer a middle-income man vehicle in Nigeria, and this represents one of the social costs of e-hailing transport for Lagosians.

Conclusion

There is no one-for-all solution to the problem of transportation in any city including Lagos State. It requires a mix of strategies and policy measures. The e-hailing transport system is at present one way of reducing the difficulties and challenges that Lagosians face in the area of transportation. While it is a welcome development, this study has shown that it is only a temporary measure. Thus, the government needs to embark on holistic transportation policies that will facilitate the ease, convenience, and security with which Lagosians move from one part of the city to another.

Recommendation

Below are some of the suggestions and recommendations for improving the e-hailing transport system and transportation system in Lagos State generally.

1. Ride-sharing: The future of ride-sharing can only be guaranteed and sustained for a long time if ride-sharing is encouraged. By this, the researcher means multiple persons on one ride on the same route should be encouraged. This will help to a large extent to solve the problem of **affordability** and may help to curb traffic/road congestion in the long run as many people may be discouraged from putting their vehicles out since they can get to where they are going with the least cost and in the ambiance of comfort and convenience.

2. Regulatory Body: There is a need for a regulatory body to be put in place to help foster a harmonious relationship between the drivers and the e-hailing platform management on one hand, as well as between the riders and the drivers on the other hand especially on an issue

which the management of such platforms find it difficult to have an amicable solution between the parties involved. In addition, the establishment of such a body that looks into the welfare of the e-hailing drivers and riders will help to ameliorate nefarious activities such as scams and ensure fair hearing, and security, among others. Such a regulatory body will also need to look at the **commission charged** by these e-hailing platforms. At present, many drivers complained that the 25% commission is too much to be deducted from them on every trip made. The body in conjunction with the e-hailing platform management will need to constantly embark on the orientation of both the Drivers and Riders on rules and regulations to adhere to promote standardization of the system. The regulatory body will also help to ensure good policies both from the government and the e-hailing companies and facilitate fair prices that will serve the interests of the different parties on the e-hailing transport system.

3. Car Loans / Hire Purchase Vehicles: Affordable e-hailing cars and vehicles with minimal upfront deposits need to be provided for more youth who are willing to engage themselves through the e-hailing transport system. By so doing, the government will be solving at least two direct problems – transportation and unemployment problems, which will go a long way to reduce youth restiveness and social vices. The Lagos State Government must be applauded in this regard as the Lagos State LagRide scheme is fashioned in this mode, though, some of the interested drivers complained about the amount of money they are expected to deposit before being given such vehicles.

4. Functional Roads: Bad roads are a major challenge to transportation in any city like Lagos State. This is because bad roads increase the number of hours motorists spend on the road trying to maneuver their way around potholes such that a journey of one hour may end up becoming a journey of five hours resulting in traffic gridlock and wear and tear of vehicle parts. The Lagos State government must constantly ensure that roads are in good shape to ensure the free flow of traffic. The government needs to work on main and feeder roads across the state to encourage more investments in the transport sector. Thus, there is a need for the expansion and creation of better road networks to reduce the vehicular pressure on the major roads in Lagos.

5. Proper Monitoring of Law Enforcement Agents

The Lagos State Traffic Management Authority (LASTMA) officials are doing a yeomen job but the bad eggs among these officials are casting them in a bad light. It is therefore important that monitoring teams are put in place to checkmate the excess of these erring officials and ensure that the culprits among them are brought to book from time to time.

6. Metro Lanes and Buses

Fast lanes and mass transport buses need to be provided across the nooks and crannies of Lagos State to discourage the number of private cars we have on the roads. Buses are by design able to carry several passengers at a time which ten to twenty vehicles may not be able to transport. They become more effective when there are designated lanes for them without having to struggle with private vehicle owners on the roads. This the Bus Rapid Transit (BRT) is meant to solve, but due to limitations in the number of routes they ply and their inadequacy in terms of number, many Lagosians are still stranded at motor parks and bus terminals. The government may need to partner with private individuals to provide such services for efficiency and large-scale operations.

7. Strict Enforcement of Traffic Laws: Without laws, human society will be a jungle. The fact is that some of the traffic gridlock in Lagos State is mostly caused by human factors such as illegal parking, illegal picking of passengers by commercial buses, and disobedience to traffic rules like failing to obey traffic lights, among others. The government enforcement team needs to look into a workable system and technology that will ensure people who run afoul of traffic lights are made to suffer the wrath of the law. It is in this regard, that the installation of traffic cameras by the Lagos State Government is a welcome development. The government needs to ensure that more of these cameras are installed at strategic places and monitored for efficiency.

8. Metro Train Service

Trains by their design can convey two hundred to five hundred passengers at a time. Although it is capital intensive, it is no doubt one of the lasting solutions to solving the problem of transportation in Lagos State. To this extent, the kickstarting of the Lagos Blue Rail Line by the government of Governor Babajide Sanwo-Olu is the right step in the right direction. There is a need for quick installation of needed facilities that will help to ensure the kick-starting of

the Red Rail Line along the Agbado / Ikeja to Yaba axis. The Yellow Rail Line must also be looked into for Lagos State to minimize the bottleneck Lagosians face in the area of transportation.

9. Strategic Aerodrome

Often, emergency operations are common experience in cities, the Lagos State government perhaps in partnership with private enterprises will have to create strategic aerodromes for the landing of helicopters for emergency health or fire services.

10. Investment in Drones

With drones, more essential services are now being provided by experts to residents of urban. Such services include the transportation of blood by drones, drugs by drones, and even basic commercial goods. Drones are by their designs smart and fast and hardly affected by the hustling and bustling of cities. The government needs to encourage academic institutions and scholars within higher institutions in the state to embark on the manufacturing of specific problem-target drones that will make Lagos State a functional and livable city.

11. Ferry Services

Lagos State is a cosmopolitan city surrounded by water. The government of the State needs to take advantage of these water resources by ensuring that a sizeable number of its inhabitants commute from one part of the State to another place. To do this, there will be a need for intentionality, political will, and huge investment in water transportation facilities, effective security systems, and constant education of the citizenry on the benefits of water transportation as a veritable alternative to road transportation.

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